

Navigating Living Labs

Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs

Submitted for the SCORE project as
Deliverable 2.4 – *CCLL Knowledge & Lessons Learned*

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	1
Why read this guide?	5
2. Coastal City Living Labs: The Basics	7
Fundamentals of Living Labs	7
Living Lab Management	9
CCLLs in Practice – the SCORE Project	11
3. Lessons Learned	19
Problem Space	20
Solution Space	33
Sustainability Considerations	40
4. Living Labs & European-Funded Projects	47
Benefits of European Funding for Living Labs	47
Maximising Potential through Project Design	48
Work Package Considerations	53
Fostering a Collaborative Environment	54
Sustainability and Project Closure	55
5. Implementation Best Practices: SCORE Case Studies	57
Ecosystem-Based Adaptation – Piran CCLL	58
Sensor Deployment – Oeiras CCLL	61
Flood Maps – Sligo CCLL	62
Risk Maps and Projection Tools – Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL	65
Digital Twin – Massa CCLL	66
6. Conclusion: Trust the Process	69
Contact Us	71
Appendices	72
Appendix A: Lessons Learned Methodology and Outputs	72
Appendix B: Deliverable Information	76

Key Abbreviations

CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
DT	Digital Twin
DT-EWSS	Digital Twin – Early Warning Support System
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Adaptations
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
LLIP	Living Lab Integrative Process
MCA	Multiple-Criteria Analysis
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
SCORE	Smart Control of Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
USE	User Scenario Evaluation
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction: What is a SCORE CCLL?

Living Labs: An Open Innovation Approach

Living Labs are **dynamic, open innovation ecosystems that operate in real-life environments**, fostering collaboration between diverse stakeholders to drive sustainable, user-centric innovation. By integrating an iterative feedback process throughout the lifecycle of an innovation, Living Labs ensure that solutions are continuously refined and adapted based on real-world conditions and user input. These ecosystems enable co-creation, rapid prototyping, and innovation scale-up, bridging the gap between research, policy, and practical application.

Living Labs are designed to generate long-term economic, societal, environmental, and regulatory impact. They serve as orchestrators or intermediaries among policymakers, businesses, researchers, and communities, facilitating knowledge exchange and collective problem-solving. The core strength of Living Labs lies in their ability to merge local knowledge with scientific expertise, ensuring that solutions are both innovative and contextually relevant.

Credit: Khurram Riaz

Credit: Oeiras Municipality - Communication Office

Credit: Governor's Office

The SCORE Project: Enhancing Climate Resilience in Coastal Cities

SCORE (Smart Control of Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities) was a Horizon 2020-funded project aimed at strengthening climate resilience in European coastal cities. In response to the growing threats posed by climate change, such as extreme weather events, coastal erosion, and sea-level rise, SCORE integrated SMART technologies, Nature-Based Solutions and Living Labs to develop effective, scalable, and sustainable adaptation strategies.

SCORE placed a strong emphasis on **Ecosystem-Based Adaptations (EBAs)**, which leverage natural processes to enhance coastal protection, improve biodiversity, and foster sustainable urban development. By combining EBAs with SMART digital technologies, SCORE enabled cities to enhance climate monitoring, prediction, and adaptation strategies. However, these innovative solutions must be tested, refined, and validated through real-world applications to ensure their long-term viability and effectiveness.

To achieve this, SCORE established a network of ten **Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs)** across seven European countries. These CCLLs serve as collaborative platforms where local communities, researchers, policymakers, and businesses co-design and implement climate resilience solutions tailored to their specific geographic and socio-economic contexts. Each CCLL followed a structured methodology to support its establishment, stakeholder engagement, and co-creation processes. Each CCLL was developed using a flexible framework, ensuring project goals were achieved, while allowing for contextualisation to the local context. **SCORE's CCLLs are located in:**

- 1 Sligo, Ireland
- 2 Dublin, Ireland
- 3 Oeiras, Portugal
- 4 Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain
- 5 Benidorm, Spain
- 6 Oarsoaldea, Spain
- 7 Massa, Italy
- 8 Piran, Slovenia
- 9 Samsun, Turkey
- 10 Gdańsk, Poland

Figure 1. SCORE's ten Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) across seven European countries.

Project Structure: As a Horizon 2020 project, SCORE was funded by the European Commission and implemented over a four-year period (June 2021 – June 2025). The project was structured into eleven Work Packages (WPs), each focusing on different aspects of climate resilience, co-creation, and technological innovation.

To facilitate iteration, SCORE employed a **frontrunner/follower methodology**, a common approach in EU-funded projects. This meant that for some technologies, development and deployment would first be tested for a select number of CCLLs. Following a period of reflection and adaptation, the same technologies would then be improved upon for the follower CCLLs to then implement. This approach allowed SCORE to iterate and adapt solutions based on feedback from early adopters, leading to more effective and context-specific climate resilience strategies.

Consortium Composition: SCORE brought together a consortium of twenty-eight organisations spanning academia, local governments, and the private sector. More than half of these organisations played direct roles in the CCLLs, forming the CCLL Core Teams responsible for local implementation. In addition, SCORE had dedicated technical partners developing tools, models, and SMART solutions for deployment within the CCLLs.

SCORE's strength lies in its **interdisciplinary approach**, which brings together experts in diverse fields of environmental science, climate modelling, citizen engagement, stakeholder engagement, coastal engineering, local policies and SMART sensing technologies, amongst others, all working together to build a more resilient future for coastal communities.

Figure 2. Composition of SCORE project partners based on their primary project role.

Why read this guide?

The **Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL)** concept was specifically developed for the SCORE project, making it crucial to document the insights gained. With a network of ten CCLLs across seven countries, SCORE offers a unique opportunity to compare experiences, identify common challenges, and highlight shared successes that extend beyond individual contexts. Capturing these lessons not only helps refine the CCLL model but also provides valuable guidance for future Living Lab practitioners, enabling them to build on SCORE's experiences.

Lessons learned were actively gathered throughout SCORE's four-year journey using a mixed-methods approach, incorporating surveys, online and in-person interviews, and various other engagement methods. This data was analysed and structured into themes, which are presented below. A detailed explanation of the methodology can be found in **Appendix A**.

This guide presents the key lessons learned from the creation, implementation, and evaluation of the ten SCORE CCLLs:

- **Chapter 2** provides **basics about CCLLs and the SCORE approach** to give additional context.
- **Chapter 3** contains the bulk of the **lessons learned**, offering practical insights and best practices.
- **Chapter 4** reflects on the role of Living Labs in **European-funded multisite projects**, compiling recommendations for designing and implementing Living Lab projects.
- **Chapter 5** shows how **SCORE's technologies** were integrated into the CCLLs and the importance of local contributions.

By sharing these experiences, this guide aims to contribute to the broader Living Lab community, providing actionable insights for those looking to establish, manage, or refine their own co-creation practices. Though this guide presents insights specifically from Coastal City Living Labs, the perspectives and recommendations presented are applicable for many Living Labs, especially those whose key stakeholders are the public sector and general public.

Looking for a more interactive approach to this document?

SCORE has specially developed a free, online course called "[Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#)" where you can work through this content, with additional bonus features like videos and quizzes. Upon completion, participants will receive a certificate of completion.

2. Coastal City Living Labs: The Basics

Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) serve as dynamic, real-world innovation spaces where diverse stakeholders collaboratively develop, test, and implement solutions for coastal resilience and sustainability. As a specialised form of Living Labs, CCLLs are structured around key pillars that define their operational framework. This chapter begins by outlining the fundamental elements of a CCLL, followed by an overview of the SCORE project including the project's ten CCLLs, whose activities and perspectives serve as the basis for the lessons you will explore in this guide.

Fundamentals of Living Labs

Methodology

The Living Lab Integrative Process (LLIP) framework (Figure 3) is a validated methodology utilised by the European Network of Living Labs, to design and implement Living Labs. **The LLIP process is broken down into three phases, the Problem Space, the Solution Space and the Deployment Space.** The Problem Space focuses on understanding the challenge(s) faced by the Living Lab community and identifying the specific stakeholders needed to tackle said challenge. The Solution Space works on the co-development and testing of solutions. The final phase, the Deployment Space, focuses on the implementation and scaling up of the solutions.

Figure 3. Living Lab Integrative Process (LLIP) adapted from Mastelic, 2019. Copyright ©European Network of Living Labs, 2022.

Building Blocks of a Living Lab

The foundation of a CCLL is built on **six key building blocks**, each playing a vital role in fostering collaboration, innovation, and real-world impact.

1. Orchestration:

The Living Lab works as an orchestrator, working within the specified ecosystem or community to facilitate connections by partnering up with relevant stakeholders.

2. Co-creation:

In a Living Lab, values are co-created, both for and with, all relevant stakeholders, ensuring a higher adaptation rate of the innovation by the end of the process.

3. Active user involvement:

A Living Lab actively involves stakeholders in all relevant activities, ensuring their feedback is captured and implemented throughout the whole lifecycle of the innovation.

4. Multi-stakeholder participation:

Living Labs take a holistic view on society, involving stakeholders from across the Quadruple Helix: government, academia, private sector, and civil society (see Figure 7).

5. Real-life setting:

Living Labs operate in the real-life settings of the end-users, so instead of moving the user to test sites to explore the innovations, the innovations are infused into their real-life.

6. Multi method approach:

Living Lab activities are problem-driven. Therefore, the approach used for every individual activity will be selected within this framework, including identifying which stakeholders need to be involved for addressing this specific challenge.

Figure 4. The six building blocks of a Coastal City Living Lab, adapted from the European Network of Living Labs.

Living Lab Management

A well-structured Living Lab Core Team is essential for the successful establishment and operation of a CCLL. Effective governance and management are crucial for Living Labs to successfully achieve their strategic and operational goals while ensuring meaningful long-term impact. Living Labs function as multi-stakeholder innovation ecosystems, requiring well-structured leadership and coordination to balance diverse interests, maintain engagement, and deliver tangible outcomes. To achieve this, a **Living Lab Core Team** is established, responsible for overseeing both the day-to-day operations and the broader strategic direction of the Living Lab. A Living Lab has **five key internal roles**:

Figure 5. Key internal roles of a CCLL Core Team.

Notably, some roles can be performed by the same person in some instances, but each Living Lab needs at least two individuals. Within the CCLLs, the internal roles are all performed by SCORE project partners. Going forward, we will refer to the **CCLL Core Team – these core teams are the SCORE partners that make up the management team (i.e., panel manager, project manager, etc.) for that specific CCLL.**

Stakeholder Engagement

Living Labs support collaboration across communities and diverse actors to tackle challenges that no one party can sufficiently respond to. As such, a key feature of Living Labs is their role in bringing together four key stakeholder groups: academia, citizens, government and industry. This collaborative model is known as **the Quadruple Helix Model** (Figure 6). Each of these actors plays a distinct yet complementary role in the co-creation process:

The Quadruple Helix Structure

Government & Public Sector plays a crucial role in policy alignment, regulatory support, and ensuring that the Living Lab's activities align with broader strategic goals. Public sector engagement is particularly important in projects related to climate adaptation, as the public sector supports the integration of Living Lab outcomes into official policies and frameworks.

Industry provides technical expertise, investment capacity, and access to cutting-edge technologies, products, and services that can be tested and refined within the Living Lab framework. Industry partners help bridge the gap between research and market application, ensuring solutions are scalable and sustainable.

Academia contributes research expertise, scientific methodologies, and evidence-based insights that help shape and evaluate solutions. Researchers can support innovation by designing pilot studies, analysing data, and ensuring that new approaches are grounded in knowledge and best practices.

Citizens are at the heart of the Living Lab process. Their lived experiences, local knowledge, and direct feedback ensure that innovations are practical, relevant, and user-centred. By actively involving citizens in the co-creation process, Living Labs can develop solutions that are more likely to be adopted and sustained in real-world settings.

Figure 6. The Quadruple Helix structure.

By leveraging the strengths of these four stakeholder groups, **the Quadruple Helix Model** fosters inclusive innovation, ensuring that the solutions developed are not only technically feasible and commercially viable but also socially accepted and publicly beneficial.

CCLLs in Practice – The SCORE Project

SCORE's Coastal City Living Labs

Spanning diverse geographical regions, each CCLL represents a unique ecosystem and culture where interdisciplinary teams collaborate with local stakeholders to explore innovative solutions.

Figure 7. Coastal City Living Labs of the SCORE Project.

	Coastal Erosion	Dune Erosion	Coastal Flooding	Land Flooding	Pluvial Flooding	Drought	Heat Waves	Extreme Weather	Storm Surges	Sea-Level Rise
1 Sligo, IE	🌀	🌀	🌀						🌀	
2 Dublin, IE	🌀		🌀	🌀	🌀				🌀	
3 Oeiras, PT			🌀		🌀	🌀	🌀	🌀		🌀
4 Oarsoaldea, ES	🌀		🌀							🌀
5 Benidorm, ES	🌀		🌀	🌀				🌀		
6 Vilanova i la Geltrú, ES	🌀		🌀			🌀	🌀	🌀		🌀
7 Massa, IT	🌀				🌀		🌀	🌀	🌀	🌀
8 Piran, SL			🌀			🌀	🌀		🌀	🌀
9 Samsun, TR	🌀			🌀	🌀			🌀		🌀
10 Gdańsk, PL					🌀			🌀		🌀

Table 1. Overview of the CCLL's main climate hazards.

1 Sligo, Ireland

Core Team Composition: Atlantic Technological University Sligo, Sligo County Council
Vision: An enduring and self-sustaining citizen science coastal cooperative integrated in Ireland's northwest to co-create inclusive and innovative approaches toward ecologically sustainable climate solutions and resilience of coastal communities.
CCLL Features: Sligo County is home to 65,000 inhabitants, concentrated mostly in Sligo town and along the coastal countryside. There are several strands and beaches vulnerable to the impacts of climate change.

4 Oarsoaldea, Spain

Core Team Composition: Oarsoaldea Development Agency (Regional Public Body), Naider (Local SME)
Vision: Become a reference for ecosystem-based solutions and coastal adaptation in the Basque Country, through enhanced engagement of key stakeholders and citizens participation.
CCLL Features: Oarsoaldea CCLL has around 70,000 inhabitants and is a fragile territory with regard to climate change. Oarsoaldea's port is increasingly at risk of suffering economic losses. The Basque coastline also has many forests and green protected areas that are at risk due to an increase in the amount of wildfires.

2 Dublin, Ireland

Core Team Composition: University College Dublin, Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council
Vision: Co-create data-driven policies using innovative EBAs and SMART technologies to empower communities in building Dublin's coastal climate resilience.
CCLL Features: Dublin is Ireland's capital with around 2.1 million inhabitants and wraps around Dublin Bay. Key infrastructure, such as the DART train line, is at risk from coastal flooding and storm surges. Living Labs and co-creation spaces have been utilised in Dublin in previous projects.

5 Benidorm, Spain

Core Team Composition: University of Alicante and Benidorm City Council.¹
Vision: Become an international reference model city, developing innovative and cost-efficient climate adaptation solutions based on reliable and accessible climate-related data, integrating all stakeholders to create a long-term plan toward environmentally sustainable, resilient coastal communities.
CCLL Features: Benidorm CCLL is a tourist destination with substantial swings in population (70K to 400K) during the summer months.

¹ Benidorm City Council was not an official SCORE partner, but remained actively involved in the project's activities.

3 Oeiras, Portugal

Core Team Composition: Oeiras Municipality, Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento (IST-ID – Research Institution)
Vision: Co-create an inclusive climate action community through active stakeholder engagement and foster citizen awareness for the climate resilience of Oeiras.
CCLL Features: Oeiras CCLL is a large municipality located near Lisbon, Portugal and is home to roughly 172,000 inhabitants. At-risk facilities include roads, the railway from Lisbon to Cascais, pedestrian paths and historical monuments.

6 Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain

Core Team Composition: Diputació de Barcelona (Province of Barcelona), Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú (Vilanova City Council), and Serveis de Suport a la Gestió (ENT - SME)
Vision: The Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL aims to become a reference and research-technological engine, co-creating data-based, innovative, and collaborative solutions toward integrated coastal management and climate change adaptation, scaled up to Catalunya and the Mediterranean area.
CCLL Features: Vilanova i la Geltrú has a population of around 70,000 concentrated in the city centre and residential areas throughout its territory. Vilanova i la Geltrú has experience with Living Labs and hosts several key natural and protected areas.

7 Massa, Italy

Core Team Composition: University of Pisa, LaMMA (Research Institute), Pro. Ge. Com. S.r.l. (SME), MBI (SME), and CNR-ISAC (Research Institute)

Vision: Develop an inclusive open lab, meaningfully co-designing feasible science-based innovative climate adaptation solutions that leads to collaborative synergies between all stakeholders toward achieving social, economic and environmental resilience for coastal communities in and around Massa.

CCLL Features: The coastal area of the Municipality of Massa is extremely hydro-geologically fragile and very densely populated. Massa is home to around 70,000 permanent residents, but the population increases significantly during the summer and tourism months.

9 Samsun, Turkey

Core Team Composition: Samsun University

Vision: A self-sustaining Coastal City Living Lab implementing a roadmap of cooperation among all stakeholders to plan, design and scale-up nature-based solutions toward social, economic, and environmental resilience of the communities living on the Kızılırmak Basin.

CCLL Features: Samsun has up to 600,000 inhabitants. Samsun's coastal region is a key natural site, the landscape is extremely flat and surrounded by wetlands with rich biodiversity. Samsun has a substantial agricultural sector, which is a key part of the city's economy.

8 Piran, Slovenia

Core Team Composition: Science and Research Centre (ZRS) Koper

Vision: Become a pioneer in Slovenia in co-creating innovative solutions by empowering the citizens and stakeholders to collaborate in the context of climate change prevention, adaptation and mitigation.

CCLL Features: Piran town centre has 800 permanent residents, with 18,500 across the municipality. Piran attracts summer tourists leading to increased demand for fresh water, straining the already scarce supply from the coast-providing Rižana River, which is vulnerable to pollution.

10 Gdańsk, Poland

Core Team Composition: University of Gdańsk

Vision: Become a pioneer in Poland, establishing a strong network of stakeholders, able to raise awareness about climate change, and collaboratively work towards innovative solutions based on an orchestrated knowledge and experience exchange.

CCLL Features: Gdańsk is a port city with up to 487,000 inhabitants located on the Gulf of Gdańsk and situated at the mouth of the Motława River.

SCORE's Key Learnings and Outcomes

The key outcomes of SCORE are presented below. Considering this guide focuses on the lessons learned for CCLLs, it is important to understand the context in which these challenges developed and the associated results.

For a thorough outline of all of SCORE's key results, visit the [Key Achievements Page](#).

1. Making Solutions Meaningful at a Community Level through Co-Creation & Living Labs

Climate change and climate adaptation strategies have for too long been addressed by top-down processes, creating out-of-touch and disconnected solutions. **SCORE overcomes this challenge through systematic collaboration and co-creation with local stakeholders.**

Key Activities & Results

- Design, implement, and evaluate a novel **CCLL Framework**.
- Engage with stakeholders through workshops and activities using the **co-creation toolkit**.
- Empower citizens using **citizen science activities** and sensors.
- Utilise **SCORE's courses, games, and data visualisation platforms** to increase their knowledge of climate challenges and EBA solutions.

2. Increasing Data Availability within CCLLs to Support Better Decision-Making

To create effective climate mitigation strategies, high-quality local data is essential. However, many communities lack the sufficient weather data needed to do so. As such, SCORE developed a suite of tools to expand the data pool available to the CCLLs.

Key Activities & Results

- Producing reliable **climate and sea level projections, data sets and maps** at the local scale and tailored to all CCLLs, to evaluate the EBAs and other interventions to support climate resilience.
- Use low-cost **citizen science sensors** to complement institutional data, capturing more detailed data in localised areas, allowing for more robust early-warning systems.
- Deployment of the **SCORE Information Platform** which collects, stores and shares the CCLLs' heterogeneous data acquired and processed.

3. Green and Technological Tools for Climate Adaptation Strategies

Effective climate adaptation strategies must integrate green approaches with innovative technology. Relying on grey infrastructure won't fully address the root of climate challenges. Instead, comprehensive solutions are needed, like those in SCORE, that blend nature-based solutions with tools, to help visualise and understand our adaptation options.

Key Activities & Results

- Co-created socio-economic assessments of EBA interventions, using a **Multiple-Criteria Analysis (MCA)** and **Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)**.
- **Risk assessment tools** aimed to estimate the risk faced by the CCLLs after the implementation of the proposed EBAs.
- Formulation of a set of **policy recommendations** to assist decision making at the local, national and EU levels.
- Develop GIS-based **Digital Twin (DT)**, providing a virtual environment for the visualisation of different climate change scenarios.

"We have been able to put people into contact that probably never have been before."

- Chiara Cocco,
University College Dublin,
Dublin CCLL

3. Lessons Learned

Let's explore the lessons learned from SCORE's Coastal City Living Labs. These have been organised around the first two phases of the LLIP, specifically the **Problem Space** and the **Solution Space**. Notably, the SCORE project does not cover the Deployment Space, so the final "phase" covered will be **Sustainability Considerations**.

Each section will reflect the most notable challenges during this phase, however, establishing a Living Lab is not a linear process and the lessons will largely be applicable at any stage. As you create and iterate your own Living Lab, recognise its iterative nature, where returning to earlier steps is a natural and encouraged part of the process.

This chapter is broken down into the following sections:

Problem Space

- Laying the Foundation
- Maximising Meaningful Engagement with Stakeholders

Solution Space

- Maintaining Stakeholder Interest
- Balancing the Quadruple Helix

Sustainability Considerations

- Maximising Impact of Results
- Strategic Planning
- Solidify Your Network

Figure 8. Living Lab Integrative Process (LLIP) adapted from Mastelic, 2019. Copyright ©European Network of Living Labs, 2022.

Problem Space

The **Problem Space** can be described as a diagnosis of the situation for the city and the context in which the Living Lab will operate. The principal objective of this initial phase is to analyse the local context, the main needs and barriers, and relevant stakeholders that should actively be included and participate in the Living Lab. In this phase the questions of WHY should the CCLL be built, as well as WHO should be involved in the process are answered.

The first step in establishing a CCLL involves analysing the coastal city ecosystem to understand its specific context and identify key practices or problems that significantly impact it. This process requires selecting one to three focus areas and defining the long-term vision and shared goals of the CCLL beyond the project's immediate scope. A crucial part of this phase is structuring the governance of the CCLL, including outlining roles and responsibilities within the Core Team.

The next step is to identify and engage relevant stakeholders, ensuring their active participation through a structured mapping process based on the quadruple helix model. This comprehensive approach helps integrate all necessary actors to maintain a human-centric perspective. Effective communication strategies and channels should be developed to facilitate collaboration, validate assumptions about underlying problems, and identify potential barriers and enablers. Finally, preparatory steps are taken to create a safe and trusted environment for stakeholders, equipping them with the appropriate tools and methodologies to support the successful implementation of the CCLL.

Relevant SCORE Activities: Within the context of SCORE, the CCLLs identified their climate challenges (and associated needs and barriers), and the stakeholders needed to co-design and test future solutions. This took place at two separate engagement workshops in the first two years of the project. The challenges faced by the CCLLs during the Problem Space across the CCLLs were notably ubiquitous despite the unique nature of each CCLL.

Figure 9. The Problem Space and associated steps within the LLIP.

“I would not underestimate the local influence of a local network. [Pete from the Sligo County Council] knows everyone, he grew up here, he knows the community. There’s a trust relationship that he helped us with. Otherwise, we would have had to build that ourselves. And that would have taken a lot of time, and progress would have been much slower.”

- Salem Gharbia,
Atlantic Technological University Sligo,
SCORE Project Coordinator,
Sligo CCLL

Sligo CCLL, Ireland

Laying the Foundation

The initial set-up of your CCLL is hugely important for success, so take time to establish a solid foundation, ensuring that the Core Team is well equipped to address challenges further down the line before engaging with external stakeholders. The Core Team should ensure the CCLL's foundation is strong, including clear objectives and a firm direction for where time, energy, and resources will be invested. Though objectives, political landscapes, or other factors may change during the course of a CCLL's lifetime, the Living Lab can more easily adapt to these if there is a strong foundation on which to base the work.

Core Team Composition

The Challenge: Across SCORE, the CCLL Core Team composition varied considerably between CCLLs (see Table 2). Each Core Team's composition brought unique challenges and benefits. The differences in composition largely impacted resource/time availability and decision-making power. While there is no one-size-fits-all approach for a successful Core Team, consider the following insights:

- Public sector partners** are essential to the CCLL's Core Team. Climate adaptation, by definition, involves public sector decision-making and implementation, as such having these public sector partners is key to ensuring progress. Moreover, having knowledge of the communities' priorities, other relevant initiatives, and access to weather data makes public sector partners extremely valuable. Public sector partners within SCORE's CCLLs existed at various levels, each of which brought their own advantages.
 - Provincial-level partners** provided the CCLLs with a holistic awareness of provincial priorities, political timelines and other relevant initiatives. These partners were valuable when it came to contributing to climate adaptation plans, connecting with other Living Labs, promoting at events, and providing guidance on funding opportunities. Provincial level partners were careful to not show favouritism to a specific community over others within the province, which can limit their inputs within the Living Lab.
 - Regional-level public sector partners** while having a good awareness of the region's needs and provided a holistic overview, faced notable challenges. Regional-level partners do not have the authority for local-level decision-making (i.e., implementing weather sensors) and similarly to the provincial level, must balance the interests of all localities without showing favouritism. In a research context with pilot sites, this can be particularly challenging as it was not always feasible to implement technologies within all the region's communities.
 - Local-level public sector partners** were extremely adept at facilitating decision-making and supporting stakeholder engagement activities. Those public bodies in smaller CCLL communities were particularly valuable due to their intimate relationships with community members and other local departments.

- Academic partners** were the main drivers of SCORE's CCLLs. Academic partners typically had larger budgets due to their dual role as researcher/technology developer and CCLL Core Team. Five CCLLs had academic partners based in their city or town. The physical proximity to the research sites and stakeholders was advantageous and increased understanding of the local community context.
- Private sector partners** in SCORE's CCLLs were not typical "industry" partners. Three SCORE partners were considered private sector partners, however, two of the three were from SME-style research institutes, while the other was an SME serving a similar function to a public sector partner. None of SCORE's private sector partners represented an industry whose business interests were directly impacted by climate change (i.e., tourism or road works). Broadly, the SME partners faced less bureaucracy, often making them more agile when hiring or purchasing equipment than their academic and public sector counterparts.

Recommended structure: We recommend having at least one partner in the Core Team from research and one from the local public sector for CCLLs to effectively run the climate adaptation activities. It is vital that these two organisations work as one cohesive unit.

Core Team Members: A successful Core Team was comprised of charismatic, committed, and self-motivated individuals dedicated to the objectives of the CCLL. It was useful to have members local to the area, as they likely already had connections and understood the local context from the start. A more local approach was hugely beneficial for identifying key stakeholders and building trust within the community. Core Team members that take initiative, continuously seek opportunities, and holistically engaged with the process got the most out of the project. Implementing a Living Lab is not necessarily an easy process, so it's important to be open to change and willing to adapt.

Quadruple Helix	Public Body			Academic		Private Sector
	Level	Provincial	Regional	Local	City-Based	
Sligo, IE				1	1	
Dublin, IE				1	1	
Oeiras, PT				1		1
Oarsoaldea, ES			1			1
Benidorm, ES				1*		1
Vilanova i la Geltrú, ES	1			1		1
Massa, IT						3
Piran, SL					1	
Samsun, TR					1	
Gdańsk, PL					1	

*Not a SCORE Consortium partner.

Table 2. Core Team composition of the SCORE CCLLs.

“Regularly using communication channels between the more technical and the more coordinating/social parts of the project are essential to guarantee collaborative work and an accessible and understandable language for all partners.”

– Sara Soloaga,
NAIDER,
Oarsoaldea CCLL

Oarsoaldea CCLL, Spain

Core Team Cohesion

The Challenge: Living Labs are people and relationship-focused, this applies not only to the relationship with stakeholders but within the Core Team. Each CCLL Core Team comprises individuals or organisations with varying backgrounds, expertise, and ways of working. Bringing together diverse perspectives, whilst innately supporting a larger co-creation goal, can cause challenges in fostering rapport and a shared vision.

Different organisations have differing schedules and timeframes, leading to logistical hurdles when coordinating workshops, meetings and activities (i.e., private sector partners often operate on shorter timelines than public bodies). Moreover, many of the Core Teams had not worked together before SCORE and because the first in-person CCLL workshop was not until month twelve, the opportunity to foster cohesion from the outset of the project was limited. SCORE was intended to have kick-off meetings in-person, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, this was not possible.

Recommendations: Establishing rapport and trust from the project's outset is crucial. CCLL Core Teams with previous professional interactions had an advantage over those CCLLs who did not. It won't always be possible to work with an established Core Team network, so to achieve this collaborative spirit more quickly, CCLLs should hold regular meetings (i.e., bi-weekly or monthly). These gatherings allow the Core Team to discuss CCLL activities, to share knowledge, and build trust. Informal gatherings such as coffee breaks, lunches, or other social events are extremely important in fostering meaningful relationships.

SCORE CCLL Example: Members of the Massa CCLL and Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL Core Teams had worked together previously on initiatives and projects. Because of this previous experience, they had a head start in team building.

“The secret perhaps is people and relationships, like interpersonal relationships, that's the core of it. If you can work and just interact with other people effectively, then that will create a team that will be able to work together. It's about identifying people and then using the structure.”

- Pete Murtagh,
Sligo County Council,
Sligo CCLL

Levelling the Playing Field

The Challenge: SCORE is a large and intricate project with 28 total partners. The Core Team composition and expertise within each CCLL varied and was often disparate. Some partners had strong technical expertise that made sensor installation a breeze, while others were experienced in co-creation and communicating with stakeholders. These compositional differences meant not every partner was equally familiar with all aspects of SCORE's terminology and methodologies. Many Core Team members struggled to understand the CCLL concept and associated technologies for quite some time. This caused uncertainty and confusion, leading to some delays within the CCLLs, particularly when connecting with stakeholders.

Recommendations: Living Lab Core Teams should be trained by each other (or other relevant entities) on the Living Lab and technical methodologies using tangible and clear examples. Training for communication and dissemination (both internal and external) is important to ensure meaningful engagement.

SCORE held monthly CCLL board meetings to provide much-needed guidance on project activities and address queries. Further activities included establishing a project-wide FAQ page and Gantt chart to provide more project management support to the CCLLs. Lastly, the [SCORE Online Learning platform](#) hosted courses that allowed CCLLs to upskill in different project elements – such as EBAs or Living Lab methodologies.

SCORE CCLL Example: The Living Lab roles (i.e., panel manager, project manager) were presented and allocated at the first CCLL workshop. This meant the CCLLs simultaneously learnt about the Living Lab roles and assigned the roles amongst themselves. Had the CCLLs been given more forewarning about this role allocation, the Core Teams could have been provided with more time to assess their staff capabilities and assign responsibilities more meaningfully.

“You do really need the local partner with a direct line to the stakeholders... if you want to be effective and on the ground, you really need someone there to open the door.”

- Mar Riera Spiegelhalder,
Serveis de Suport a la Gestió,
Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL

Living Lab Branding

The Challenge: Within each CCLL, the Core Teams engaged with stakeholders using various CCLL names, most commonly one of the following: CCLL name, SCORE or a relevant local institution (i.e., Sligo CCLL, SCORE, or Sligo County Council). Those using the CCLL name were required to spend additional time educating stakeholders on the Living Lab concept as it was often a new concept and unclear for many of the CCLLs' stakeholders. Those using an academic or municipal institution's name benefited because of the pre-established credibility. Lastly, those using SCORE found it was easy for participants to understand the role of a project, however, as SCORE ended or as the CCLL engaged in other projects or initiatives, it was difficult to create a clear link between those activities and SCORE.

Recommendations: From the start of the CCLL, ensure your Core Team discusses a clear title for your Living Lab. There is no “one size fits all” solution for how you should brand your CCLL. Regardless of your choice, make sure you are aware of the pros and cons of the choices available to you, be consistent and consider future sustainability. Establish a “brand” to improve the visibility of your CCLL; create a central communication channel and email, determine your CCLL's name, and develop clear brand guidelines for communication (a logo, colour palette, etc.).

SCORE CCLL Example: In larger communities with multiple ongoing initiatives, such as in Vilanova i la Geltrú, Oarsoaldea, Oeiras, or Dublin, the CCLLs found it easiest to conduct activities under the “SCORE project” title. In Sligo, Gdańsk, and Samsun, the Core Teams consistently used the title of CCLL to engage with stakeholders and found this useful for the CCLL's continuity and using the CCLL for other projects. In the case of the Gdańsk CCLL, they saw their CCLL as an entity somewhat separate to SCORE. In turn, they've been able to leverage that entity into new European-funded projects (i.e., Pro-Climate), highlighting the sustainability of the CCLL.

“We are trying to sell the brand of the Living Lab. We had the vision that we are interested to last forever... we want to have new projects, not only SCORE, but other activities which will be closely linked to the SCORE project...”

- Katarzyna Barańczuk,
University of Gdańsk,
Gdańsk CCLL

Mapping the Landscape

At the early stages of Living Lab development, it is necessary to dedicate time and resources to properly investigate the larger ecosystem your Living Lab will operate within. This includes the political landscape and policy timelines, and external resources, like data availability.

Political Will & Interest

The Challenge: Regional and local politicians were often limited in their ability to support the CCLLs. This was often due to conflicting priorities within the locality, an inability/unwillingness to implement changes ahead of upcoming elections, and resource constraints. Local politicians are important stakeholders, and their support was often needed to implement proposed solutions, causing challenges. Lastly, not all political priorities aligned with the CCLL's climate adaptation goals, creating hurdles in advancing the initiatives.

Recommendations: Core Teams should be aware of current political priorities and understand when/how to capitalise on policy. Identify early on the key policies and relevant timelines that can or should be targeted and how the Living Lab intends on contributing. Be conscientious of the cyclical nature of local, regional, or national governments; think long-term about how your project could adapt should the political landscape change. Knowing the ins and outs of the political system is not always easy, so include public servant champions within in the Core Team who can stay up-to-date on these challenges.

SCORE CCLL Examples: Sligo CCLL, with the support of the Sligo County Council partner, identified the Irish Climate Action Plan as a key policy to target at the onset of SCORE and adjusted their work plans to ensure contributions were submitted at appropriate times. As such, they achieved this goal and had great success in formally incorporating the results of the CCLL into the wider Sligo Climate Adaptation Network. In the case of the Dublin CCLL, they were able to incorporate their recommendations on EBA approaches into their local Climate Adaptation Plan. Unfortunately, they were unable to incorporate some of the stakeholder engagement activities, as the workshops were not in alignment with the timeline for submission.

Data Availability

The Challenge: Access to the data was a challenge for most CCLLs, stemming from bureaucratic hurdles and processes. Every country had different rules, regulations, and cultural practices around sharing data; some CCLLs even noted that competitiveness between institutions could hinder sharing. City councils and other relevant authorities may not be at liberty to share all required data or may require a data sharing agreement. Further, communities may generally lack the data or software required to run certain models.

Recommendations: Establish meaningful relationships with public bodies and relevant data holders (i.e., academics). By cultivating strong relationships, trust and cooperation can be fostered, leading to smoother access to data. Living Labs should explore alternative data sources; this may involve tapping into European data sources or existing community surveys or collecting additional data through citizen-science activities.

SCORE CCLL Example: In the Oarsoaldea CCLL, some public agencies showed little interest initially in sharing data. Interestingly, once the team established a relationship with a scientific centre that had established trust with these agencies, they were able to gain access to data from institutions that had previously been uncooperative. This highlights the importance of networking and trust-building as key strategies for overcoming collaboration barriers.

Maximising Meaningful Engagement with Stakeholders

With the foundation of your CCLL securely established, we now move to stakeholder engagement. These initial interactions provide stakeholders with a first impression of the CCLL and Core Team; stakeholders need to be valued and feel that they bring something necessary and impactful to the Living Lab. This section will address common stakeholder engagement challenges retention, ensuring representation across the Quadruple Helix and managing diversity.

Managing Purposeful Participation

The Challenge: Due to busy schedules, the cost of participation for stakeholders can be high. Stakeholders may experience frustration if they feel their time is not serving a greater purpose or aligning with their values. This will decrease the chances of their returning for future events.

Recommendations: There should always be a clear objective when engaging with stakeholders, so make sure to clearly communicate the added value of their participation. When planning, identify the components and questions that truly require stakeholder input, prioritising their time and energy. Consider who in your pool of stakeholders is most needed based on the event's objective. It is important not to reinvent the wheel or create participation fatigue. Look for areas of overlap to optimise stakeholder engagement across tasks and activities, and even potentially with other Living Lab projects in your community.

Ahead of any stakeholder engagement activity, reflect on the following:

Key Questions to Maximise Collaboration

1. Why are the stakeholders here?
2. How will you use their feedback?
3. Are there opportunities for collaboration to minimise asks?
4. Can you prioritise what information is shared?

SCORE CCLL Example: Within Benidorm CCLL, there was some misalignment between the local schedule and SCORE's project schedule. Specifically, SCORE's EBA prioritisation workshop took place after the Benidorm City Council had decided (with relevant stakeholders) which EBA solution to implement. While the workshop was able to gather additional insights, the immediate, short-term benefits were less evident to participants, lessening investment in the process. However, Benidorm CCLL is optimistic that these findings will be utilised for future EBA implementation.

Setting the Stakeholder up for Success

The Challenge: The Quadruple Helix Model (Figure 6) ensures that all aspects of society are represented and consulted during co-creation scenarios. Engaging with a heterogeneous pool of stakeholders from various backgrounds, disciplines, and perspectives is not simple. What may be a simple activity for one stakeholder, could prove to be more difficult for another due to varying backgrounds (i.e., culture, education, profession). In the same workshops ran by different CCLLs (i.e., MCA Workshop in Gdańsk vs Piran), some stakeholders reported the materials being too simplistic, while others said they were too complicated.

Recommendations: Do not assume a stakeholder's level of understanding. In advance of the session, distribute relevant materials (agenda, key terms, etc.). At the outset of a session, provide a general overview using simple language and defining terms. This reduces the burden on the stakeholder to ask a "silly question" and increase their confidence in voicing an opinion.

Validate the perspective of all attendees, reiterate that all opinions are valuable and encouraged, and invite quieter participants to share their opinion.

Coffee breaks are a good time to connect with quieter participants and answer their questions. This proactive approach allows stakeholders to familiarise themselves with the topics, engage more meaningfully, ultimately leading to more productive outcomes.

SCORE CCLL Example: At a Dublin CCLL co-creation workshop, many of the present stakeholders were public sector experts working on similar water and climate-related projects. One single person representing a local community group was present, but notably did not share opinions as often or as freely. When this stakeholder was specifically asked their opinion and invited to share, they opened up and had many novel insights that the technical stakeholders had not yet shared. It is important to use methods that ensure all voices are heard and feel empowered to share their perspectives.

"[The stakeholders] thought they were 'not good enough for academics'... we always told them no, [your perspective] is so valuable for us... we learned so much from them."

– Neslihan Beden,
Samsun University,
Samsun CCLL

Event Design

The Challenge: Designing events to suit Quadruple Helix stakeholders can be difficult. The success of an event depends heavily on the facilitation team and the session's logistics. Different types of attendees will show up depending on the time of day, duration, or day of the week.

Recommendations: Successful engagement relies on a flexible facilitation team and a context-specific plan. Compile a list of attendees in advance to anticipate possible questions and tailor the presentation to the group.

Facilitation should ideally be in the local language, using lay terminology where possible, and technical jargon should be explained. Be prepared to manage difficult conversations and keep conversations relevant to the session's objectives. Distribute a feedback survey following the session to identify what worked and what could be improved for future events. Provide materials (digital or paper) as necessary to complete any task and ensure technology is accessible. Have extra technology (i.e. smart phones, laptops or tablets) and paper versions available.

"We made sure that [after workshops] if [some stakeholders] were shy or couldn't attend... we would always explain everything to them that we talked about."

– Neslihan Beden,
Samsun University,
Samsun CCLL

"You must be prepared to identify the relevant stakeholders, but most of all to interact with them. To engage, not with a huge group of persons, but relevant persons of each stakeholder group."

– Maria Manuela Portela,
IST-ID,
Oeiras CCLL

Event Considerations

Consider which people from the **Quadruple Helix Model** are most essential to have in attendance for the session objectives and plan accordingly:

Time of Day: Weekday, day-time sessions are best for professionals, such as government actors, policymakers or academics, but get less engagement from the private sector and private citizens who are understandably busy with work and family. The reverse is true for evening or weekends, with higher private sector and citizen engagement, but less professional representation. Consider which part of the Quadruple Helix Model is most essential to have in attendance for the session objectives.

Location:

- **In-person sessions**, especially at relevant sites (i.e., pilot areas) are more engaging and promote open-discussions more easily than online, while allowing for informal relationship building. However, in-person sessions are more resource intensive for both the CCLL and stakeholders.
- **Online sessions** allow for more flexibility and have a lower barrier to entry. Online sessions can be very useful for information sharing, but less valuable for intensive or challenging discussions.

Number of Sessions: To achieve co-creation goals, Living Labs can divide activities into multiple, shorter sessions, or fewer, longer sessions.

- **Multiple shorter sessions** require less time commitment per day but retaining the same participants over multiple sessions is challenging. As participants come and go, comprehensive summaries of the progress are necessary.
- **Singular longer sessions** allow for more in-depth discussions (formal and informal) and are better for any in-person or onsite activities. However, this large commitment may dissuade participants from joining.

Figure 10. Event Considerations for stakeholder engagement sessions.

Solution Space

The **Solution Space** begins with ideation, where diverse ideas are generated, explored, and refined through methods such as brainstorming, mind-mapping, and sketching. This process helps create innovative solutions, which are then transformed into prototypes (early representations of products, services, or experiences) allowing users to interact and provide feedback. The goal is to develop solutions that address the challenges identified in the Problem Space, foster behavioural change, and new sustainable practices.

Following prototyping, pilot interventions are implemented in real-life settings. These pilot tests help refine prototypes, identify gaps and validate assumptions before a full-scale roll-out. Testing and user feedback loops are critical, enabling iterative refinement of products and services. The process encourages knowledge sharing and learning from failures. Evaluation is the final component of the Solution Space, involving structured assessments of stakeholder engagement, project effectiveness, and long-term impact. These assessments provide valuable insights for improving the innovation process and scaling up successful solutions.

SCORE: As part of the Solution Space, CCLLs engaged with stakeholders to conduct Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) to prioritise the best EBA solutions, worked alongside communities implementing weather sensors as part of citizen science activities, and sought iterative feedback on various SCORE technologies (i.e., Financial Resilience Tools & Digital Twin).

Figure 11. The Solution Space and associated activities for the LLIP.

Maintaining Stakeholder Interest

As the CCLLs move into the Solution Space, the lessons learned focus predominately on stakeholder engagement, including knowing when and how to engage with stakeholders for specific activities, and managing their priorities. It is particularly important during this stage to ensure stakeholder interest and prolonged engagement of the Quadruple Helix is maintained.

Community Building

The Challenge: Sustainable and successful Living Labs require stakeholders to participate and engage. At this stage, CCLLs must consider how to maintain relationships with their existing stakeholder, whilst also expanding the network and engaging new stakeholders.

Recommendations:

- 1. Build trust and relationships:** Community building is at the core of all Living Lab activities - relationships and trust are what make a CCLL successful; stakeholders want to feel valued and have a personal connection to the CCLL. SCORE's CCLLs found that their best use of time was spent building and maintaining relationships at a personal, one-to-one level, rather than at an organisational level – people do the work, not organisations.

- 2. Keep track of stakeholders:** Events and stakeholder engagement activities may be inconsistent over a project/period. As such, contacts should be catalogued (consider using a customer relationship management system), allowing the Living Lab to build a stakeholder pool for future events.

- 3. Engage in their spaces:** Do not exclusively engage with stakeholders in academic or government settings – meet them where they are at. Utilise “third spaces”, such as pubs, cafes, beaches, community centres, or churches within the community to reach wider networks and create more diverse engagement. Identify community events your Living Lab can participate in to increase visibility, such as science expos or local fairs.

- 4. Utilise the informal time:** The significance of informal/unstructured time cannot be undervalued. Chatting at coffee breaks and allowing stakeholders to connect with each other, leads to much more meaningful discussions, creates buy-in, and increases future participation.

- 5. Follow-Up & Stay Connected:** Connect with stakeholders after the event, follow-up with action points and highlight the value of the attendees. Share the results of the session via newsletter or personal email, or post the event on social media. If a policy or initiative is impacted by this work, ensure stakeholders know and are acknowledged. Running big and engaging events on a routine basis is not practical and often not necessary to achieve the CCLL's objectives; sharing small actions and periodic updates on results can be enough to keep the members engaged.

“A lot of [the stakeholders] want to work collaboratively with the county council. They want to find solutions... Pete [from Sligo County Council, Sligo CCLL member] would usually reach out to them and they trust him a lot... That gave us a way to contact and connect with them. Sligo is a smaller community, so it was easier to form those one-to-one personal connections.”

– Ananya Tiwari,
Atlantic Technological University Sligo,
Sligo CCLL

SCORE CCLL Example: The Piran CCLL found that individuals are more willing to collaborate compared to organisations, and engaging with them through informal one-to-one meetings was the most fruitful, especially with difficult-to-reach stakeholders. These meetings took considerable effort to organise and manage, but the stakeholders felt valued. In Sligo CCLL, a SCORE PhD Candidate was able to engage organically with the stakeholders when doing data collection on local beaches, chatting with curious beachgoers, explaining the Living Lab and Sligo CCLL's work. This organic interaction fostered some of the strongest stakeholder connections within the CCLL.

“Regardless of your perspective, let's work together... we have to collaborate; everyone, everybody.”

– Neslihan Beden,
Samsun University,
Samsun CCLL

Giving Responsibility to Engaged Stakeholders

The Challenge: Living Labs are always limited by resources, whether this is time or financial.

Recommendations: Get more people involved in the CCLL and expand the Core Team to include trusted stakeholders. Find opportunities to share the load, especially with those with greater geographical reach, resources, or linkages. Stakeholders can take responsibility for running events, managing social media, supporting community engagement or sharing data.

Consider how to incentivise stakeholders to join the CCLL Core Team and benefit from this additional responsibility. Highlight the Living Lab as a good networking opportunity for professionals or provide work experience for students. Consider appointing CCLL stakeholder “champions”. A clear title/role can encourage engagement across organisations, for individuals and students alike, increasing the overall capacity of the CCLL.

“At the beginning, we tried to solve all problems with just the Core Team. We didn’t give any responsibility to other stakeholders... When we started giving them responsibility, we saw that they are doing it, and they were involved. We should have done this earlier than we did.”

– Şule Haliloğlu,
Samsun University,
Samsun CCLL

SCORE CCLL Examples: Samsun CCLL was successful in recruiting post-secondary students to take on various roles within the CCLL to support implementation, while the Sligo CCLL has partnered with a nationally embedded beach clean-up organisation to support community engagement. In a larger capacity, the Benidorm CCLL has partnered with Benidorm City Council (who is not a SCORE partner) to be a part of the Core Team, thereby increasing capacity and sustainability for the CCLL.

“If you don’t have strong organisations, you need to have really active citizens... It took us a long time to find them... senior citizens are amazing when it comes to this. If they are interested, they will do a lot of promotion and engaging with others.”

– Erik Kralj,
ZRS Koper,
Piran CCLL

Balancing the Quadruple Helix

Engagement with Private Sector Actors

The Challenge: Considering the Quadruple Helix Model, CCLLs primarily had participation from academics, public sector, and civil society/citizens, with the lowest engagement from the private sector/industry. Priorities between the private sector and the CCLLs were often not aligned, and most SCORE workshops took place during working hours when businesses and industry are typically unavailable. Further, climate adaptation timelines are at a longer scale (over years), while private sector tends to work on shorter time scales.

Recommendations: While engagement across the Quadruple Helix is a key pillar of Living Labs, it is not necessary to have equal engagement with all sectors. The CCLL’s aims were to improve climate adaptation and resilience and therefore engagement with public sector, academics and the general public were most important. Accordingly, resources were allocated to focus on those three sectors.

To engage with the private sector (or any difficult to reach sector) more effectively, consider their motivations for engaging. What makes your Living Lab attractive to them? Are there shared objectives between your Living Lab and their organisation? As always, build relationships slowly and keep them informed of the work, but don’t overburden the team and utilise resources if the reward will not outweigh the effort.

SCORE CCLL Example: A few CCLLs were able to engage with industry stakeholders, most notably Benidorm CCLL. Benidorm CCLL worked closely with the hotels who are concerned about their beaches as tourism is key for this community. Specifically, climate sensors and cameras were placed on hotel roofs to monitor variables including coastal erosion. In exchange for their support, Benidorm CCLL provided the hotels with the data and findings.

“With industry, maybe we just have to find what incentivises them more... maybe we just need to figure out what the stakeholders need from us.”

– Ananya Tiwari,
Atlantic Technological University Sligo,
Sligo CCLL

Managing Expectations

The Challenge: Each stakeholder has unique perspectives and priorities; this can result in conflicting needs/requests from Living Lab stakeholders. CCLLs found that individual citizens and civil society groups had the most strongly held views about climate adaptation, as their homes and communities were directly suffering from the climate hazards. Two recurrent points of tension arose:

- Timelines between academic research and citizen priorities often do not align. Climate adaptation research moves slowly, while citizens are (understandably) hoping for big(ger) solutions on a shorter time scale. High expectations from citizen stakeholders are often in contrast to the available resources, causing conflicts regarding research priorities and the final outcomes of the project.
- CCLL co-creation sessions give citizen stakeholders direct access to local government representatives, often leading to citizens raising a range of concerns beyond the specific Living Lab task.

Recommendations: Be clear what actions are (or are not) in the Living Lab’s scope, reducing the likelihood that stakeholders become misinformed about upcoming activities. Facilitators need to confidently and considerately navigate tough conversations, reminding the stakeholders what is feasible and keeping on task. Remind stakeholders that the results of a specific topic will likely not be finalised after one session; other perspectives of absentee stakeholders or additional research considerations may need to be incorporated.

SCORE CCLL Example: Oeiras CCLL engaged with ambitious stakeholders who ultimately had larger goals than would be feasible within the timeline of the SCORE project. They managed this during the workshops, by clearly outlining what options were available to stakeholders within their specific context.

“I tried to keep expectations at a reasonable level... [we would] stress the fact that we are not there to solve the problem, but to provide a roadmap on how to proceed to work together toward the objective.”

– Filippo Giannetti,
University of Pisa,
Massa CCLL

Targeting Policy

The Challenge: Targeting policy is a common and highly impactful objective for CCLLs. Policy timelines can be quite long, and preparation of new policies or adaptation of existing ones can start years before finalisation. Climate adaptation policies are developed and implemented at differing policy levels (i.e., national vs regional) and are often interlinked with various sectors (i.e., urban planning and economic development), meaning that policy inputs must be coordinated across multiple departments and political bodies.

Decision-makers may lack technical expertise or familiarity with climate resilience solutions, leading to hesitation or resistance to change. Even with a clear policy plan, policymakers are often inundated with policy briefs and requests for engagement, so getting their time and attention can be a challenge for CCLLs.

Recommendations: Continue building upon the foundation set during the Problem Space, aligning your objectives with existing policies, plans, and networks. Highlight where possible your collaborations within the CCLL with local businesses, academia, NGOs, and citizen groups, to create broader political momentum. Policymakers are more likely to act when they see public demand and cross-sectoral support for proposed initiatives. By proactively engaging from the onset with government agencies, city councils, and regulatory bodies, you can position your work as a valuable contribution to policy goals, rather than an external demand for change.

Provide policy makers with clear, concise, and visually engaging communication materials. Given their limited time and competing priorities, policymakers need easily digestible materials that highlight key findings, actionable recommendations, and the benefits of proposed solutions.

SCORE CCLL Example: Sligo and Oeiras CCLLs both developed locally relevant [policy briefs](#) for policymakers. Notably, the Sligo CCLL followed this with an online seminar to share this brief and CCLL results with various members of the Sligo County Council staff, which was useful to give a more thorough overview of their recommendations and build further relationships.

Various materials and presentation of results, including infographics or videos providing overviews, activities and results, [GeoStories](#), and [Massive Open Online Courses \(MOOCs\)](#), have proven effective in translating complex concepts into accessible formats for policymakers. High-level decision-makers may prefer the succinct policy briefs from SCORE, while technical advisors have benefitted from different technologies such as the [SCORE ICT Platform](#).

“We have the role as being the catalyst, trying to listen to all the voices to then try to find the middle floor going forward.”

– Cécil Meulenberg,
ZRS Koper,
Piran CCLL

Sustainability Considerations

During the final months of the project, whilst activities remained in the Solution Space, the CCLLs co-currently were working on a transition to life beyond SCORE. Given the project's frontrunner/follower methodology and various other local considerations (i.e., Core Team composition, future funding opportunities, etc.), this preparation has been different for each CCLL. At this point, the CCLLs focused on **solidifying stakeholder networks** and **dissemination of results**.

Maximising Impact of Results

The Challenge: Maximising the impact of SCORE's results required ensuring that findings were accessible, understandable, and actionable for the right stakeholders. CCLLs often struggled to recognise their role in co-developing results, particularly for those technical outputs which were mainly developed by technical partners. This led to difficulties in accessing, understanding, and integrating these results into their work, and overall reduced the feeling of ownership. Additionally, many outputs were highly technical, available only in English, or required specialised expertise, creating barriers to widespread adoption.

Recommendations: Promote shared ownership and tailor results for usability to increase impact. Encourage CCLLs to take ownership of project findings by highlighting their role in co-development and conducting knowledge transfer sessions. Appointing stakeholder "champions" who play key roles in development can reinforce accountability and motivation. Additionally, adapting materials to different audiences, using visual tools like GeoStories, simplified infographics, and policy briefs (as relevant), ensured accessibility. Translating key materials into local languages and using open access/easily accessible platforms further improved uptake and usability.

SCORE CCLL Example: Within Vilanova CCLL, both public administration bodies have strict restrictions on the software available to the institution's computers. Specifically Python, a software used for some SCORE results, was not accessible, these colleagues struggled initially to use specific results, causing delays and reduced motivation.

"There are people on the academic side of things doing some really exciting research that is important to show to the other stakeholders. From where I am, in the local authority, being able to bring the academic side to the community, to the ground; being able to be that link has been a privilege and something really useful to me."

– Pete Murtagh,
Sligo County Council,
Sligo CCLL

Strategic Planning

For CCLLs to thrive beyond their initial phases, adaptation, and resource acquisition are essential. Reassessing objectives ensures alignment with evolving policy landscapes and stakeholder needs and securing further resources, whether financial or human, is crucial for sustainability. Proactively seeking new funding opportunities and fostering local partnerships can help CCLLs transition into self-sustaining entities with long-term impact.

Revisit Objectives

The Challenge: As a CCLL moves along the various LLIP phases, the current landscape in which you are operating will change, such as the Core Team composition, involved stakeholders, relevant policy cycles, etc., causing misalignment between the CCLL's strategies and the current ecosystem.

Recommendations: The CCLL strategic plan needs to be reassessed periodically and potentially realigned. Assess the future ecosystem and the feedback previously received from stakeholder networks. Are there additional policies or initiatives you want to contribute to? Further stakeholder groups you want to engage with? Ensure your Core Team is on the same page again and ensure you are moving into the next phase as an aligned, cohesive unit.

Resource Allocation

The Challenge: The CCLLs' main recurring challenge was a lack of resources - either time, human, or financial. Sustainability beyond initial funding is a key consideration for ensuring the long-term impact of Living Labs.

Recommendations: If funding is your main challenge, begin looking early for additional funding and ensure you are on track for applications relevant to this. Be proactive and consider allocating a member of your Core Team to such a task. Such efforts are not only critical within the context of Horizon funding but are equally applicable to any Living Lab aiming to achieve long-term success and impact.

Networking is a key part of funding procurement, so use your existing contacts to build your CCLL into future activities and projects. When strategically assigning effort, consider whether it is a better investment to improve underperforming areas, or rather, lean into areas of success. For example, reaching certain demographics (ages 25-40, the private sector, etc.) has been consistently difficult across the CCLLs. However, CCLLs have been successfully engaging with youth and students. Rather than focus on this challenge, leverage the engagement with students to connect with their parents. Find opportunities to lean into the success, to better use resources. Finally, be aware of procurement and hiring timelines within your institutions when planning the next phases of the project as this can be quite resource intensive.

SCORE CCLL Example: As a four-year EU-funded project, SCORE's CCLLs faced the reality that the project's funding would end. For example, the Sligo CCLL used resources within their academic institutions to look for and apply for additional funding opportunities, ensuring the CCLL's sustainability.

"We have learned a lot over the four years of the project. We weren't aware what a Living Lab methodology was at first... and it was a bit challenging to involve stakeholders... but we see the greater acceptance of the solutions, and our idea in the future is to scale up this methodology and solutions and replicate this in the neighbouring cities and expand our collaboration."

– Ignacio Toledo Sepulcre,
University of Alicante,
Benidorm CCLL

Solidify Your Network

The following lessons reflect on best practices to ensure the CCLL's stakeholder relationships and network will continue beyond the Solution Space and SCORE, and even be scaled up into new initiatives.

Reflecting on Progress

The Challenge: Due to busy schedules, setting time for reflection can be overlooked. This is a missed opportunity for important reflection and improvement.

Recommendations: Any successful Living Lab involves successful and thoughtful iteration, this applies not only to the technologies and activities, but to the CCLL itself. Taking time to debrief and reflect may not always seem like a priority due to busy schedules, however having open and honest conversations within the Core Team can improve the CCLLs function and efficiency. Reflect on challenges to date, assess opportunities to improve communication internally, enhance stakeholder engagement, and capitalise on successes.

"[Running a CCLL] takes time, and you cannot focus on everything. Establishing CCLLs is not just here and there a workshop which is officially a project activity. It takes interaction and time and personal talk, and that should be reflected somewhere as having the funds as a partner to do these kinds of things."

– Cécil Meulenberg,
ZRS Koper,
Piran CCLL

Internal Knowledge Transfer

The Challenge: Core Team and stakeholder institutions can be huge, meaning colleagues within institutions may not be aware their organisation is a member/founder of a Living Lab. Over the course of a CCLL's lifetime, the active individuals may change (i.e., change in roles, availability, etc.). If a key Core Team member or stakeholder leaves their institution without onboarding their replacement/new colleagues, delays and confusion, or loss of previously established contacts can result.

Recommendations: In reality, we make connections with people, not organisations: it is the responsibility of the Core Team to ensure that colleagues within their own organisations are very familiar with their CCLL work (i.e., continued updates on the CCLL's progress via email). That way, in the case that roles change and an individual needs to leave the project, the institution remains embedded in the Living Lab structure. This is true also for key stakeholder groups: whenever possible, ensure you have reliable connections with multiple individuals within any given institution. In turn, Core Team members should seek to connect their own colleagues with other CCLL participants and share knowledge about their activities.

SCORE CCLL Example: In the Samsun CCLL, the Core Team established strong ties with a contact from a multinational corporation as part of their corporate social responsibility programme. This individual unfortunately left the corporation within the duration of SCORE, and their replacement was not aware of the project or as keen to get involved, resulting in a need for new negotiations, which was inefficient and ultimately disappointing.

"If you don't find the right person in that organisation, or your contact person doesn't open up to the next colleague, then it takes longer... it takes a lot of time for people to trust you and see there is potential that projects like these can aid in the common goal, in which people can collaborate."

– Cécil Meulenberg,
ZRS Koper,
Piran CCLL

Keeping Momentum

The Challenge: Many CCLLs risk stagnation if they do not actively seek new partnerships, synergies, or alignment with other stakeholders, projects, initiatives or Living Labs.

Recommendations: A huge success of SCORE was the CCLL support network, which allowed for knowledge sharing and peer-support. Throughout SCORE, CCLLs relied on one another for advice and support in periodic, facilitated knowledge sharing sessions. Whether you are part of an official Living Lab network or not, prioritise building your own peer Living Lab network.

At a local scale, continue to maximise engagement with the community. Set aside time specifically to identify new projects or other collaborations (i.e., stakeholders or Living Labs). Consider who is working in your area that you can synergise tasks with (such as finding mutually beneficial events). By strategically leveraging existing connections, CCLLs can strengthen engagement and position themselves for continued success.

SCORE CCLL Example: Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council (Dublin CCLL's County Council partner) is part of [Smart Dún Laoghaire](#), an initiative aimed to "future-proof" Dublin and implement projects like SCORE. As such, DLRCC was able to coordinate on behalf of the Dublin CCLL, to create connections with other projects. In Piran, the CCLL Core Team identified other community actors, including those working with a local heritage centre with overlapping interests, that allowed them to be present at other events.

In Sligo, the CCLL linked in with clean-up groups to promote citizen science activities at their volunteer days. Further, through SCORE, Oarsoaldea has become involved in another regional sustainability project. They built-on their SCORE activities, integrating the philosophy of co-creation and Living Labs, and leveraging the close relationships created with stakeholders, into this new initiative.

"The main thing is communication, engagement, development of relationships. Trying to provide what is asked of you as quickly as possible, as efficiently as possible and to participate in things like this. That engagement piece, that relationship piece, it's so important, because if you don't have that, it's not really going to work."

– Pete Murtagh,
Sligo County Council,
Sligo CCLL

4. Living Labs and European-Funded Projects

Because SCORE placed its Coastal City Living Labs at the heart of the project, it was essential not only to examine how they operated with their stakeholders and within their local contexts (as was shown in **Chapter 3**) but also to consider how SCORE's overall project design impacted the CCLLs' success. The increasing importance of stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and collaborative innovation methodologies has made Living Labs a core component of many Horizon Europe projects, as such, understanding the interplay between project structure and Living Lab effectiveness can provide valuable lessons for future Horizon projects seeking to implement similar approaches.

No project is ever flawless, and while SCORE created and established a successful network of CCLLs, there is always room for improvement. The following sections reflect on what worked well, the challenges encountered, and recommendations for future projects aiming to maximise the impact of Living Labs within Horizon Europe.

Benefits of European Funding for Living Labs

- **Budget and Duration:** European funding (i.e., Horizon Europe) provides Living Lab projects with pre-established budgets, clear project objectives, and timelines. Giving both financial security and clarity over activities for the project's duration.
- **Long-Term Collaboration:** Horizon Europe facilitates long-term collaboration between partners, both within the Living Labs and across the consortium. Allowing meaningful relationships to be formed, increases the likelihood for future collaboration and sustainability of the Living Lab.
- **Future Funding:** Living Labs can leverage their project outcomes to secure future funding opportunities through new research initiatives, municipal partnerships, or further EU funding. These programmes provide potential pathways for continued investment in climate adaptation and resilience-building efforts. For example, the Sligo and Gdańsk CCLLs have already leveraged more funding for their Living Labs through the Pro-Climate Project.

"A big success is the network that was established... those connections are not simple connections... they can stay after SCORE or for life. The ground is laid... not only within the CCLL, amongst the Core Team and stakeholders... but with the other CCLLs."

– Michele Sacco,
LaMMA Consortium,
Massa CCLL

Maximising Potential through Project Design

Living Lab Design

SCORE implemented ten CCLLs across seven countries, each with unique compositions and governance structures. While this wide geographical scope allowed for diverse knowledge sharing, it also introduced challenges in coordination, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability.

Best Practice CCLL Core Team Composition: SCORE's CCLL Core Teams are composed exclusively of the SCORE consortium partners, with one exception. These Core Teams have varying compositions, ranging from one academic partner to three partners (an academic, municipal and provincial partner) to many other combinations (see Table 2). Core Teams with only one partner had challenges in balancing workload, while Core Teams lacking community ties (i.e., the Core Team institutions were based elsewhere and/or the Core Team didn't have a representative from the local community) had challenges with stakeholder engagement. Specifically, the absence of municipal partners in the Core Team resulted in greater implementation and stakeholder engagement challenges, leading to a reliance on external, non-partner entities.

Recommendations:

- A municipal public administration partner is a must for each CCLL Core Team and necessary for climate adaptation work. The municipality provides credibility, policy awareness, and access to local networks/stakeholders.
- Maintaining a minimum of two partners per CCLL to improve project continuity and mitigate capacity risks during busy seasons.
- Include all Core Team members in the consortium; consider who are key partners for future implementation and have them formally involved in the grant preparation stage, rather than relying on their voluntary participation during implementation.

"We have three different institutions, so it gives us a different perspective, different skills, so when you bring them all together, it allows us to achieve different results. We have an SME which is really close to the research side; we have a local administration that in the end if you need to do something, they have the stakeholder networks and the access to the technical institutions; and then we have an administrative institution at the provincial level which helps improve and increase the dissemination of results."

– Mar Riera Spiegelhalter,
Serveis de Suport a la Gestió,
Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL

"In the beginning it was complex for [some stakeholders] to understand our project, as there are many activities... so they wanted to know the results they would get from our project... but every year it got easier as we could show our advantages and tools."

– Katarzyna Barańczuk,
University of Gdańsk,
Gdańsk CCLL

Gdańsk CCLL, Poland

How many CCLLs is the right number? The more Living Labs within the project, the bigger the network, the more opportunities for knowledge sharing and cross-pollination of ideas between Living Labs. But as with all things, there are drawbacks. The decision to implement ten CCLLs was ambitious, and while it facilitated a wide-reaching network, it also created logistical and administrative challenges. The recommendation here is not on the perfect number of CCLLs, but rather to consider that each CCLL needs a meaningful budget. Many CCLL Core Team members dedicated personal time and energy, outside of their working hours and project budget, to maintain relationships with stakeholders. Allowing for more budget per CCLL (and thereby more personnel) would reduce the burden faced by individual staff and the risks of delays.

Recommendations: Each CCLL needs budget for two separate partner organisations (i.e., a municipal partner and academic partner) and a meaningful budget, allowing individuals to dedicate a significant portion of their working time to the Living Lab for the full project duration.

Where should the Living Labs be located? Having a geographically diverse group of CCLLs allowed for a broader range of insights and sharing across cultures and countries. Implementing at least two CCLLs within the same region can facilitate more informal collaboration and in-person engagement, due to shared cultural or political environments. Interestingly, SCORE's Spanish CCLLs found having a shared language, and geographic proximity was beneficial, allowing them to meet more informally during the project. Ultimately, however, most CCLLs felt that the location or country of other CCLLs did not impact their ability to collaborate and learn from their experiences.

"We are more connected to [the other CCLLs in Spain], probably because the Spanish language is a link. But we also collaborate with them on [various SCORE activities]."

– Xabier Sema Korta,
Oarsoaldea Development Agency,
Oarsoaldea CCLL

Frontrunner vs. Follower Methodology: A common practice in European-funded projects is to have replicators, fellows or follower cities. While the terminology differs, the idea remains the same, some Living Labs do the activities first and typically in a more robust manner, and a second wave follows. In SCORE, the frontrunner vs. follower structure intended to create a system of knowledge transfer, whereby more advanced CCLLs (frontrunners) would support and guide less developed CCLLs (followers).

This hierarchical approach, theoretically, allows frontrunners to share their experiences, methodologies, and best practices, allowing followers to accelerate their own progress. The feedback on this system amongst CCLLs was mixed – some followers appreciated the support, while others found it confusing and lead to unbalanced results despite still requiring substantial effort from the CCLLs. This was largely dependent on the project element that the CCLL was a frontrunner or follower in and their experience with that specific output.

Notably, the lack of equity through which frontrunner and follower roles were attributed across work packages, made the experiences less comparable than if the CCLLs were ubiquitously frontrunners or followers.

Rather than a frontrunner/follower model, future projects could consider a "buddy system". A buddy system, whereby CCLLs are paired thematically by climatic challenges (i.e., coastal erosion and flood risk management), would increase engagement and collaboration, creating clear partnerships within a bigger overall network. By fostering peer-to-peer collaboration, rather than a uni-directional transfer of knowledge, this system would ensure that shared learnings are more relevant and applicable, and reduce the disparity between partners, creating a more balanced and effective knowledge-sharing framework.

"I think it was nice [to be a frontrunner] because we have more products and outputs to show, and a wider vision of the project. We also had the opportunity to collaborate with a larger number of partners."

– Xabier Sema Korta,
Oarsoaldea Development Agency,
Oarsoaldea CCLL

“The ultimate goal is for the CCLL to operate independently of me and my team. A CCLL should be able to sustain itself, grow and evolve without our direction anymore. This means empowering them to take on leadership roles in the management board, building a CCLL structure that doesn't rely on the [SCORE] CCLL Core Team.”

– Neslihan Beden,
Samsun University,
Samsun CCLL

Samsun CCLL, Turkey
Credit: Samsun Governor's Office

Work Package Considerations

Designing work packages effectively is essential to structure a successful and impactful project, as this determines how different components interact, responsibilities are distributed, and knowledge is transferred. **The experience of SCORE highlights several key considerations for structuring work packages effectively.** Consider the following:

- Living Lab projects need a minimum of three years to ensure sufficient time to build relationships, develop and implement the Living Lab frameworks and disseminate the results - best practice would be **4-5 years**.
- CCLLs found that results/activities with a **strong community focus**, such as the Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA), sensor workshops, or the [Ecosystem-Based Adaptation \(EBA\) catalogue](#), were the most impactful for the locality. Other outputs, like the maps, which provided much needed data for the communities were also very valuable.

Networking Considerations:

- Have a **specific partner** responsible for coordinating all the CCLL's activities, including learning exchanges. This role was critical in SCORE to maintain engagement, timeliness, and knowledge transfer.
- Projects need **specific tasks and budget** for reflection, knowledge sharing, and dissemination. Collecting lessons learned was invaluable, not only for the development of such a deliverable, but for the CCLLs and coordination team to reflect and address risks in real-time.

Build in Flexibility: Each Living Lab must work within the restrictions that their unique environment provides them. For example, each CCLL was required to collate local data for the technical partners, and for some CCLLs this process was quite challenging due to local practices/availability. With ten Living Labs in SCORE, it was difficult to ensure that all CCLLs could simultaneously achieve the same outcomes. As such, it is important to ensure the task and work packages have some flexibility built in to manage these risks and challenges.

Integrate Technical Partners with the Living Lab Core Teams: One of the main coordination efforts in SCORE was ensuring strong integration between Living Lab partners and technical partners. CCLLs with core partners who were also leading technical tasks or work packages (usually an academic partner) had an advantage as there was a direct connection between technical development and local activities. When possible, appointing Work Package/Task Leads from within the CCLL Core Teams can strengthen the link between technical development and practical implementation, increasing motivation and ensuring better alignment with local activities.

Fostering a Collaborative Environment

Bridging the gap between Technical Partners and CCLL Core Teams: A fundamental challenge in multidisciplinary projects like SCORE, is ensuring effective communication between technical and non-technical partners. Given the diverse backgrounds of participants, ranging from data engineers to public servants to communications experts, misalignment in expectations, terminology, and working styles, is almost unavoidable at times but it does create collaboration barriers. Many CCLLs initially struggled to fully grasp SCORE's technical methodologies/tools, while technical partners lacked insight into the practical constraints faced by municipalities and local actors. Holistically, many partners struggled to understand the Living Labs concept until nearly a year into the project.

To bridge the communication gap between technical and non-technical partners, training sessions should be built into the project design to cover the basic principles of the project, including the technologies, stakeholder communication and Living Lab basics. Encouraging interdisciplinary discussions from the outset can help create a shared language and prevent misunderstandings later in the project.

“[It's important to have] someone with the specific skills to communicate and stimulate and translate the very technical concepts. [This] would be useful in the future to make people understand the real value of the project.”

– Roberta Paranunzio, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Massa CCLL

Create an Empowering Environment: A key role of the coordinator and coordination team is fostering a sense of ownership and pride within CCLL teams. This can be achieved by showcasing success stories, emphasising the real-world impact of their efforts, or involving them in decision-making processes. Particularly at early stages of the project, some partners lacked a sense of ownership over their CCLL, perceiving their role as secondary to the project's technical aspects, rather than central to its success.

Encourage Self-Directed Collaboration: Encourage CCLL teams to connect with peers in a more self-directed way. While structured exchanges were valuable, some CCLLs remained largely dependent on project coordinators to facilitate connections, rather than actively seeking out other Living Labs in a self-directed way. This limited the potential for informal knowledge-sharing and the cross-pollination of ideas.

“We can be sure that our work is going to continue into the future because it has worked for many years in the past.”

– Rafael Ocaña Barbero, Diputació de Barcelona, Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL

Sustainability and Project Closure

Sustainability and project closure are often difficult topics in collaborative research projects, particularly when working with multiple Living Labs. Many Living Labs rely heavily on the structure, resources, and coordination provided by the project, and without clear pathways for continuation, they may struggle to maintain momentum after funding ends.

Sustainable Core Teams: Diverse partner composition strengthens sustainability. Academic institutions play a crucial role in securing future research funding and providing continuity as seen in Samsun, Dublin, Gdańsk, amongst others. Municipalities, like Vilanova i la Geltrú, that have been actively involved throughout the project are more likely to integrate CCLL initiatives into their long-term planning. By ensuring a balanced mix of partners from the outset, Living Labs can be better positioned for long-term success.

Continue Engaging: To ensure continuity, Living Labs should integrate with existing regional adaptation efforts and ongoing initiatives. Establishing a Community of Practice among project Living Labs can help maintain networks, preserving relationships and expertise beyond the funding period. Informal networking opportunities, such as community forums or thematic working groups focused on shared challenges like coastal erosion or urban flooding, can further strengthen connections. By fostering these relationships outside of project-led activities, CCLLs can enhance long-term collaboration and sustain their impact well into the future.

Identity and Branding: Without a clear strategy for how CCLLs should present themselves post-project (i.e., SCORE vs CCLL), there is a risk that their work becomes fragmented or loses visibility. Living Labs should create a post-project strategy amongst core partners. For example, Dublin CCLL, specifically the academic partner and municipality, have discussed what the Living Lab will look like after SCORE to establish a post-project identity.

“The Dublin CCLL should have been an entity... A logo, email – centralise everything... so the stakeholders would have been engaging with the Dublin CCLL. I think that would have been a good way to ensure the lifetime of the CCLL.”

– Chiara Cocco, University College Dublin, Dublin CCLL

Graceful Close Out: The expectation that CCLLs will transition seamlessly from project-funded initiatives to fully autonomous entities is not always realistic. Instead of aiming for full autonomy at project closure, projects should adopt structured exit strategies that enable a graceful close for those CCLLs who need it; ensuring the Living Labs conclude their activities meaningfully, rather than abruptly. These strategies could include finalisation workshops with stakeholders, transition roadmaps, and guidance on securing future funding, and should always account for the stakeholders' perspectives. It is essential that CCLL stakeholders remain informed and reassured that their contributions continue to matter, and even if the work evolves, the core priorities of the partnership/organisations remain unchanged. Before the project ends, results should be shared, contact information updated, and stakeholders assured that the team remains available.

5. Implementation Best Practices: SCORE Case Studies

In the previous chapter, we explored the lessons learned from the Problem and Solution Space, with Sustainability Considerations. So – what did these activities look like in practice?

Within SCORE, the ten CCLLs were tasked with various activities and technologies that were to be implemented through the project. We share five case-studies about how the CCLLs combined the strengths of creation and SCORE's technologies.

1. **Piran CCLL – Nature Meets Heritage:** Community-led workshops blended traditional knowledge and green innovation to build climate resilience while preserving cultural identity.
2. **Oeiras CCLL – Sensors in Action:** Low-cost sensors and local collaboration help communities monitor coastal changes and adapt to climate risks.
3. **Sligo CCLL – Smarter Flood Forecasting:** Satellite data, sensors, and citizen input power erosion tracking and flood prediction.
4. **Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL – Risk-Informed Planning:** Financial risk tools support climate investment decisions and strengthen the case for nature-based solutions.
5. **Massa CCLL – Real-Time Resilience:** A Digital Twin and Early Warning System developed to support and guide urban planning.

"[The stakeholders] want to see some action in their territory... SCORE was a starting point to build something that is real and useful for the population and the territory."

– Roberta Paranunzio,
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche,
Massa CCLL

Ecosystem-Based Adaptation - Piran CCLL

The CCLLs, using the guidance and methodologies of SCORE, worked with stakeholders to co-create a list of priority **Ecosystem-Based Adaptations (EBAs)** to enhance climate resilience in their communities. EBAs, sometimes referred to as Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are types of green infrastructure (i.e., green parks, marram grass, etc.). These adaptation approaches focus on ecosystem restoration and enhancement of ecosystem services to protect society against negative impacts of climate change. The EBA team within SCORE developed the [SCORE EBA Catalogue](#) to educate stakeholders at these workshops and present best-practice examples of EBA implementation across Europe.

The EBA prioritisation workshop centred around what is referred to as a [Multi-Criteria Analysis \(MCA\)](#). The MCA framework has been designed to allow stakeholders to evaluate EBAs based on their economic, social, and environmental value, ultimately creating a prioritised list of EBAs that the community has jointly agreed are most valuable.

The **Piran CCLL** served as a leading example of successfully implementing the MCA workshop as part of their Living Lab. Piran is a historic town, with an extensive cultural heritage, which faces severe freshwater shortages during summer. These unique circumstances posed unique opportunities for climate adaptation. Through the MCA process, Piran CCLL, as well as planting trees, also prioritised rainwater collection through historic cisterns. They also emphasised the importance of existing traditional practices, such as water-permeable pavements and dry-stone wall techniques to be implemented in small patches of available green areas, as impactful potential EBA solutions. Notably, the selected EBAs were different than initially identified in the project planning, showing the value of stakeholder input. The engagement of conservation experts and historians further enriched the decision-making process, ensuring that climate adaptation measures aligned with cultural preservation goals. The Piran CCLL recognised the potential for revitalising historical infrastructure in general for modern climate adaptation strategies.

Following this prioritisation, the Piran CCLL took the research a step further and conducted a cost-benefit analysis for these adaptation measures to better understand the implications of this work. Local stakeholders were incredibly necessary in this process due to cultural heritage regulations. Specifically, in Piran, non-invasive methods must be used to assess infrastructure like rainwater collectors and water-permeable pavements before renovation. Archival research and historical literature helped locate blueprints and construction details, bridging historic research with urban climate adaptation. This work engaged authorities, historians, and citizens, fostering renewed interest in the town's heritage while enhancing climate resilience and maintaining its tourist appeal.

This work by the Piran CCLL showed the importance of tailoring EBA strategies to the specific geographical, social, and cultural context. While nature-based solutions are widely recognised for their environmental benefits, their successful implementation depends on community engagement and historical continuity, making Living Labs the key environment to engage with these activities.

"Through mutual interaction and interest, there is a lot more awareness about climate adaptation and how to implement this through the cultural heritage which is present and with limited resources and limited area they have."

—Cécil Meulenberg,
ZRS Koper,
Piran CCLL

Piran CCLL, Slovenia
Credit: Municipality of Piran

“It was great to have the university because they have the scientific knowledge, the scientific point of view of the project, and the municipality has the important connection with the schools... So, both the scientific and the practical.”

– Teresa Carmo Vaz,
Oeiras Municipality,
Oeiras CCLL

Oeiras CCLL, Portugal
Credit: Oeiras Municipality – Communication Office

Sensor Deployment – Oeiras CCLL

SCORE set out to **improve data availability** within the CCLLs to better monitor coastal changes, ultimately strengthening decision-making tools and increasing climate resilience. To achieve this, the CCLLs engaged their wider stakeholder networks through **sensor selection workshops**. These workshops helped identify the most appropriate coastal sensors based on each CCLL's priorities, whether that meant using numerous low-cost sensors to involve more citizens or opting for fewer but higher-quality sensors to enhance institutional monitoring.

The selection of citizen science sensors was guided by the [SCORE Sensors Catalogue](#), an online platform that compiles information on affordable, easy-to-deploy sensors designed to monitor key environmental factors in coastal cities worldwide. Once selected, the sensors were installed with the help of local citizen scientists, ensuring community ownership of the initiative. The data collected fed into the [SCORE ICT Platform](#), making it accessible for CCLL use and for the development of tools such as the Digital Twin.

The **Oeiras CCLL** stands out as a strong example of effective collaboration between municipalities, universities, and civil protection agencies in deploying citizen science sensors. Through sensor selection workshops, the Oeiras CCLL worked with local actors to determine the most suitable sensors for their needs. However, challenges arose, including delays due to project timeline alignment and difficulties in purchasing certain sensors in Portugal. To navigate these issues, the team sourced similar sensors locally while ensuring they met environmental monitoring requirements. This adaptive approach not only allowed the project to proceed smoothly but also led to the inclusion of these alternative sensors in the catalogue, demonstrating the importance of flexibility in technology deployment.

A key success of the Oeiras CCLL was integrating the deployed sensors into the existing municipal grid, enabling real-time data collection that supports civil protection agencies in monitoring inland and coastal flooding risks. Schools also benefited from the initiative, incorporating the sensors into educational programmes to raise awareness of environmental changes. While engagement with schools required navigating complex administrative procedures, the CCLL Core Team successfully established a formal protocol to ensure long-term collaboration.

This work in Oeiras highlights the value of continuous iteration between technical leads and CCLLs within SCORE. The collaboration between universities, municipalities, and SCORE technical experts has not only strengthened the Sensors Catalogue, but has also laid the groundwork for a lasting citizen science sensor programme beyond the project itself.

Flood Maps – Sligo CCLL

A major challenge in effective climate adaptation is the lack of sufficient data and understanding of diverse climatic and geographic conditions. Within SCORE, this challenge was addressed through the generation of high-resolution climate and sea level projections tailored to local coastal challenges. To generate these models, all the CCLLs worked with local stakeholders to improve data availability and understand high risk areas, amongst others.

In **Sligo CCLL**, the community faces significant climate challenges, specifically coastal erosion and flooding. Stakeholder engagement has been central to Sligo CCLL's success. Workshops involving local authorities, environmental agencies, and community groups helped identify gaps in coastal risk assessments. These sessions underscored the urgent need for improved storm surge forecasting and extreme sea level predictions, particularly in areas previously understudied in Sligo. With these insights in hand, and concerns about the coastal erosion and flooding, Sligo CCLL developed relevant computational models.

Shoreline erosion studies were conducted using the CoastSat model, analysing historical satellite images to track shoreline changes over time. To improve accuracy, drone surveys and the SCORE Photobooth Coastal Initiative were introduced. This initiative, co-developed with Dublin CCLL, allows citizens to contribute real-time shoreline images, creating a unique dataset that enhances scientific research. The crowdsourced data is especially valuable in areas where satellite imagery is limited due to cloud cover or resolution constraints.

Coastal flooding and **storm surge forecasting** have also been key priorities. Using advanced hydrodynamic models, Sligo simulated storm surges and predicted extreme sea levels. These models are supported by locally deployed water level sensors that provide real-time monitoring of sea levels. The collected data is accessible through a mobile app, making it easier for citizens and stakeholders to track flooding risks. Additionally, GIS and mapping software have been used to generate detailed flood forecast maps, giving authorities and communities a clearer understanding of high-risk areas.

By integrating multiple data sources, satellite imagery, drone surveys, low-cost sensors, and citizen science, Sligo CCLL has developed a comprehensive coastal monitoring system. This approach provides policymakers, urban planners, and researchers with accurate, real-time data to support climate resilience and sustainable coastal management. Key achievements include the creation of baseline erosion maps for northwest Ireland, the identification of high-risk areas, and the development of storm surge forecasting models essential for disaster preparedness. At the same time, the initiative has strengthened knowledge-sharing between researchers and local communities, ensuring a more collaborative and informed approach to coastal adaptation.

*"We got the right team,
working with the right people,
at the right time."*

– Khurram Riaz,
Atlantic Technological University,
Sligo CCLL

Sligo CCLL, Ireland

Risk Maps and Projection Tools – Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL

One challenge in climate adaptation is determining the optimal timing and approach for investments to maximise returns. As such, SCORE developed **two key results, financial risk profiles and a Decision Support System (DSS)** to help municipalities assess climate-related risks and make informed financial planning decisions.

The risk profiles, built on probabilistic flood risk assessments, provided a detailed understanding of potential financial losses from flooding using local data on population, infrastructure, and economic exposure. Specifically, the risk profiles included an overview of how EBAs might mitigate climate risks and associated costs. The DSS integrated these findings into a single platform, to support municipal decision-making and evaluate various financial strategies tailored to the specific risk landscape of the CCLLs.

One of the most significant outcomes was the practical application of these tools is resilience planning. The DSS allows municipal authorities to simulate financial strategies and assess trade-offs between different approaches to risk mitigation. The integration of EBA effectiveness into risk assessments also provided compelling evidence for investing in nature-based solutions, reinforcing their role in the city's long-term adaptation strategy.

The inclusion of the CCLL and local partners was essential to getting the tools to a useful and contextualised place. **Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL** kicked off these activities by collating all the necessary data needed to shape the exposure models. Co-creation sessions with municipal representatives emphasised the importance of visualising financial impacts in an accessible format, leading to refinements in the accessibility and usability of the DSS. Further, the EBAs incorporated into the risk profiles were selected during further co-creation sessions with local stakeholders, ensuring that solutions reflected regional priorities and constraints.

The experience in Vilanova i la Geltrú highlights several key takeaways for other cities looking to implement similar technologies. Early stakeholder engagement ensures that risk assessment tools are tailored to local needs, while training municipal staff in using tools and interpreting outputs enhances the effectiveness of decision-making. By leveraging co-creation and data-driven insights, the Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL has set a strong precedent for other coastal cities seeking to enhance resilience in the face of climate change challenges.

"I think we were really brave to be frontrunners... I think it was risky from our side, but we feel really proud... it's been hard work, but the benefits have been greater."

– Ester Toledo,
Vilanova i la Geltrú City Council,
Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL

Digital Twin – Massa CCLL

The **Massa CCLL** served as a key pilot site for the implementation of SCORE's Digital Twin and Early Warning Support (DT-EWS) System. The DT-EWS system was designed to help municipalities monitor real-time conditions, simulate extreme weather events, and assess potential flood impacts. The aim is to improve urban resilience by providing an integrated platform that combined predictive modelling with real-time data from sensors and weather forecasts.

The **DT-EWS** has two main components, the **User Scenario Evaluation (USE)** and the **Early Warning Support (EWS)**. The USE provides user-friendly visualisations of flood risk, models hypothetical climate scenarios, and tests the effectiveness of Nature-Based Solutions. By contrast, the Early Warning Support (EWS) subsystem can provide live alerts based on sensor readings and weather forecasts, helping emergency managers prepare for potential disasters. This integration of predictive and real-time analytics offered a more comprehensive approach to flood management compared to traditional tools, also providing a finer spatial resolution.

To start building Massa's DT-EWS system, the Massa CCLL played a crucial role in supplying essential data to the development team. This included high-resolution maps, land use information, river geometry, and climate data, which were uploaded to the project's data repository, [SCORE ICT Platform](#). The DT system was calibrated to Massa's local conditions, a process that required standardising the diverse data formats. Once operational, the DT-EWS continuously took-up real-time data inputs from weather stations and hydrological sensors (including those implemented through SCORE's citizen science activities) in Massa, enabling the DT-EWS to generate flood risk projections and, when relevant, issue timely alerts to municipal authorities.

The DT-EWS was first developed for Massa CCLL, revealing several lessons learned. Standardising and integrating diverse datasets requires significant effort due to the many inconsistencies in data formats and units of measurement. Additionally, engaging local stakeholders early on was critical for ensuring the system met the needs of target users, particularly Massa's urban planners and civil protection agencies. SCORE DT developers and the Massa CCLL facilitated two user engagement sessions to get feedback from these users in order to more clearly tailor the system to their needs. Massa's experience demonstrated the value of a co-design approach, where feedback loops between developers and users helped refine the system's usability and effectiveness.

Ultimately, Massa's deployment of the DT-EWS set the stage for its adoption in other coastal cities. By combining advanced simulations with real-time monitoring, the system not only improved flood preparedness but also facilitated strategic urban planning. The pilot highlighted the importance of local adaptation and stakeholder involvement in making Digital Twin technology a practical tool for climate resilience.

"I think about people coming out from the meetings and the materials like seeds in the community... they start speaking about EBAs, the Digital Twin, with friends or colleagues... now there are these kinds of concepts that could spread... I think of Massa CCLL as a seeding event, not necessarily a solving event."

– Alberto Ortolani,
LaMMA Consortium,
Massa CCLL

Massa CCLL, Italy

“We had to explain the [CCLL] concept for a good year at least... and then it took another year for people to actually spread this news amongst themselves... now they are organically trying to spread the awareness [of the concept] to the groups they are part of... It really took a long time to explain the concept but in the end people are just fully embracing it without even knowing what the term is or that it is a term.”

– Erik Kralj,
ZRS Koper,
Piran CCLL

6. Conclusion - Trust the Process

The SCORE project has demonstrated that building effective Living Labs is a gradual process that hinges on **sustained, long-term relationship building**. CCLL Core Teams have consistently focused on and celebrated the creation of new stakeholder connections through their activities. However, these relationships required **ongoing effort and investment over time**, highlighting the need to trust the process, even when immediate benefits are not apparent.

The foundation laid in the first years of the project in establishing and maintaining these ties underlines a key lesson: **while relationship-building can be labour intensive and slow, the resultant collaborations are invaluable for long-term sustainability**. These networks not only facilitate effective knowledge transfer but also ensure that the impact of the Living Labs extends well beyond the project's lifecycle. Continued engagement and regular follow-ups with stakeholders are essential to nurture and capitalise on these relationships.

Ultimately, the SCORE project reinforces the notion that the real success of a Living Lab lies in its ability to create and maintain a robust network of stakeholders. These enduring connections, though sometimes intangible, are the cornerstone of sustainable innovation and effective climate adaptation strategies. By recognising and embracing the slow, incremental progress of relationship-building, future projects can ensure that the benefits of co-creation and collaborative learning continue to flourish over time.

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Appendix A: Lessons Learned Methodology and Outputs

As part of SCORE Project's **Task 2.8 - Knowledge production and exchange**, ERINN Innovation, with the support of Work Package 2 Colleagues (IHS, Naider, ENoLL, ATU) has undertaken a comprehensive, rigorous mixed-methods approach to systematically capture lessons learned from SCORE's ten Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) to support the further establishment of CCLLs beyond SCORE.

In the early stages of the project ERINN, with the support of WP2 colleagues developed a **methodological framework and calendar** to carefully capture insights from both technical and non-technical activities, thereby providing a holistic picture of how the CCLLs have adapted and matured over time. The below methodology was developed and applied over the course of 3.5 years and involves a continuous cycle of data collection, analysis, and validation, from the Problem to Solution Phases, and considering sustainability. By engaging directly with CCLL partners through surveys, interviews, and interactive sessions (both online and in-person), the project has built a rich dataset that documents the evolving challenges, successes, and best practices of the SCORE approach.

Data Collection

Data collection was continuous throughout the project, allowing the team to establish a baseline understanding and to monitor changes as the CCLLs evolved through the Problem and Solution Phases, as well as sustainability considerations. Data collection activities included:

Surveys: The distributed Monitoring and Evaluation surveys (Task 2.7) included key "lessons learned" (Task 2.8) questions. The surveys were distributed at multiple intervals throughout the project (and at least once a year) to all 10 CCLLs to capture baseline data and subsequent changes in vision, challenges, and successes. The surveys were always distributed ahead of the 1-1 CCLL interviews (described below), providing the CCLL Core Teams an opportunity to reflect and brainstorm ahead of the online sessions.

Questions included:

- Regarding the most recent CCLL workshops, what went well?
- Regarding the most recent CCLL workshops, what could be improved?
- What are the main barriers for your CCLL in the next 6 - 12 months?
- Do you feel your team has the necessary resources (financial, technical or otherwise) to be successful? Please specify.
- What advice would you give to other CCLLs at this stage?
- Are there steps or procedures you wish had occurred earlier to facilitate your work now? If yes, what and why?
- What support does your CCLL need to communicate activities and/or results to stakeholders?

Interviews with CCLLs: Online interviews with CCLL Core Teams were integral to the data collection process for Task 2.8 and D2.4, offering detailed qualitative insights and reflection on project progress. These interviews allowed ERINN to communicate the vision and purpose behind collecting lessons learned, build relationships with the CCLLs, and most importantly, gain in-depth understanding of their progress and challenges. The sessions were not limited to WP2 tasks but considered activities across the project including the MCA workshops, sensor deployment, EBA training schools, and financial resilience tools, amongst others. The interviews were conducted during critical project milestones and after key stakeholder engagement events, enabling timely reflection while experiences were still fresh. Over the project's duration (2022–2025), all 10 CCLLs participated in annual lessons learned meetings, with WP2 frontrunners holding an additional session in 2023. A final comprehensive interview with all CCLLs further validated earlier findings and provided a holistic view of the SCORE project journey. Interview questions included but were not limited to:

Holistic SCORE Questions

- Looking back at the entire SCORE project, what do you consider your CCLL's biggest success?
- If you could restart the project, what would you do differently? What support would have been helpful but was missing during the project?
- Were there any unexpected lessons or insights gained throughout the project?
- How did your role as (frontrunner or follower) influence the outcomes of the project for your CCLL?

Stakeholder Engagement

- Was it necessary/How did you manage expectations with stakeholders?
- How has the involvement of stakeholders and the living lab approach influenced the local community?

Results and Tools:

- What SCORE tools or resources were most valuable to your CCLLs?
- Reflect on one specific result produced and how that has been useful for your CCLL.
- Did the network of CCLLs impact your work and the effectiveness of your individual CCLL? Benefits and improvements?
- For Spain and Ireland, what impact did having a CCLL in your own country impact collaboration?
- How much of a factor did data availability have in the development of your results?
- Talk to us about policy implementation and feeding into these. What practical tips do you have? Policy briefs vs other outputs?

Vision and Sustainability:

- Has your vision for your CCLL evolved since the start of the project? If so, how?
- What strategies do you have in place to maintain or expand your CCLL's activities beyond 2025?
- Do you envision your CCLL contributing to climate adaptation or other local challenges in the future?

Interviews with non-CCLL members: ERINN hosted reflection sessions with each of the technical work packages (WP1-8) alongside knowledge management activities (T9.3). These sessions enabled technical teams and partners to evaluate their engagement with the CCLLs and local stakeholders. In particular, WP2 colleagues (IHS, Naider, ENoLL, and ATU) consistently shared their insights throughout the project, both in dedicated lessons learned meetings and during monthly WP2 meetings.

Interactive Workshops: Consortium meetings and other in-person events, such as Open Living Lab Days, served both to reflect on lessons learned, sharing successes, challenges, and future barriers—and to facilitate knowledge exchange among CCLLs on topics like sustainability, EBAs, sensors, citizen science, and knowledge transfer. Formats such as “World Café” and “Asks & Offers” sessions, where participants developed a CCLL profile and discussed what they could share and where they required support, encouraged open discussion, shared learning, and collaborative problem-solving. These sessions provided rich, comparative data through active interaction among the CCLLs.

Sustainability Sessions: Five online sustainability sessions were held covering topics such as Co-Created Values, Operations, Impacts, Ownership of Results, and Stability, providing a platform for the CCLLs to exchange ideas, brainstorm, and plan for their future. During these sessions, CCLLs were divided into smaller digital breakout rooms, enabling more intimate discussions with one or two other CCLLs. ERINN utilised the process by rotating between rooms, gathering lessons learned, and summarising the key points at the end of each session. These discussions highlighted the major challenges the CCLLs face and helped identify actionable strategies for moving forward.

General Observation & Reflection: A key component of the data collection process has been the general observation of CCLL activities. To ensure a holistic understanding, ERINN has actively participated across WP2 tasks by providing support, facilitating activities, and attending select workshops. This engagement has allowed for a critical assessment of the processes. In addition, CCLL Board Meetings, along with other WP2 and knowledge transfer workshops (organised with Naider as part of T2.5), and consortium meetings, have served as essential platforms for gathering valuable observations.

Analysis

Thematic Analysis and Validation: After extensive data collection through interviews, workshops, and consortium meetings, ERINN conducted a systematic thematic analysis to distil lessons learned into key themes across the various project phases. All findings were rigorously analysed and then presented to the CCLLs and WP2 partners during consortium and board meetings, ensuring that the insights accurately reflected their experiences and challenges. Finally, the deliverable was reviewed and validated by the CCLLs, WP2, and the SCORE Coordinator, ensuring its accuracy and relevance for future initiatives.

Outputs

Two main outputs were produced to highlight the Lessons Learned collected:

- This document (D2.4) was developed over several years, compiling the lessons learned over various phases. Upon completion of the content, the deliverable underwent a significant design phase.
- Online Course – An online course was developed to be added to the suite of SCORE MOOC courses available (Developed for Task 9.6.3). The course “[Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#)” is available on the Thinkific platform, incorporating the content developed for D2.4, videos developed by ERINN and ENoLL, and quizzes. The idea of this course is to make the content more engaging for a wider audience, including CCLL stakeholders.
- [Two short videos](#) highlighting the lessons learned, considering living labs within European projects and those more generally.

Conclusion

Early data collection efforts identified initial challenges and opportunities, while subsequent rounds, integrated into regular consortium meetings and dedicated knowledge transfer sessions, allowed for ongoing refinement and deeper understanding of the collaborative processes. This iterative process fostered effective peer-to-peer learning, enabling Living Labs to share best practices, compare experiences, and adapt their strategies based on collective insights.

WP2 activities were adjusted throughout, accounting for the CCLL's main challenges in the hopes of streamlining project implementation and fostering high-quality project results based on the data. This extensive and iterative data collection process has culminated in a comprehensive Lessons Learned document that not only summarises the SCORE project's journey but also provides practical guidance for future Living Lab initiatives. By documenting and disseminating these insights, the project ensures that the hard-won lessons and best practices continue to drive long-term impact and sustainability well beyond the project's lifespan.

Appendix B: Deliverable Information

Project Details

Project Title: Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities

Duration: June 2021 – June 2025 (48 months)

Call identifier: H2020-LC-CLA-2020-2

Grant Agreement No: 101003534

Deliverable Details

Title: Deliverable 2.4 - CCLL Knowledge and Lessons Learned

Lead: ERINN Innovation (Casey Borklund, Rochelle Caruso and Jane Maher) for Work Package 2

Due date: May 31st, 2025

Type of deliverable: Report

Dissemination level: Public

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534. All information in this document only reflects the author's view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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